

This dataset was prepared for the participants in the second championship phase of the Open Challenge organized by the CHAIMELEON project for the training of AI models to resolve a specific clinical question related to Prostate cancer:

Low vs. High risk patients prediction (in order to avoid unnecessary aggressive procedures in low-grade patients and to provide the most advanced therapy for high-grade).

All 669 prostate cases (images and clinical data) collected until November 2023 were initially taken. Then 12 cases were excluded due to missing Gleason information, 13 cases due to missing baseline MRI and other 8 cases due to missing axial T2w MRI.

From the 636 resulting cases, 446 were selected for the training partition and so included in this dataset:

324 with low risk and 122 with high risk.

The original series (DICOM) with T2w and DWI images were selected and an extra series was added with harmonized T2w images in NIfTI format.

Only images from diagnosis were included in the dataset.

In the Open Challenge only demographic and diagnosis information (excl. PIRADS score and biopsy-related information) was shared with the participants, but here the complete clinical data is included in the eforms.json file.

The ground truth for the clinical question in that case was based in the Gleason score variables. Those patient with a 3+4 Gleason score or below were considered **low risk** patients while, those with a Gleason of 4+3 or above were considered **high risk** ones.

```
diagnosis_data = case['eForm']['pages'][2]['page_data']

gleason_primary = int(diagnosis_data['primary_gleason_pattern']['value'][-1])
gleason_secondary = int(diagnosis_data['secondary_gleason_pattern']['value'][-1])
gleason_sum = gleason_primary + gleason_secondary

if gleason_sum < 7: risk = 'Low'
elif gleason_sum > 7: risk = 'High'
elif gleason_primary == 3 and gleason_secondary == 4: risk = 'Low'
elif gleason_primary == 4 and gleason_secondary == 3: risk = 'High'
```

ID: b875a59a-32f0-4e47-9da6-1e635a85b370

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/b875a59a-32f0-4e47-9da6-1e635a85b370/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 446

Subjects count: 446

Age range: Between 46 years and 86 years

Sex: Male

Body part(s): PROSTATE, ARM, PELVIS, Pelvis^Masculin, ABDOMEN, Unknown

Modality: MR, Unknown